

Article

Screening Microalgae for Producing Biofuel Precursors from Industrial Off-Gases

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Abstract: The capture and conversion of industrial off-gases into valuable biomass using microalgae represents a promising strategy for CO₂ mitigation and sustainable production of biofuels and biochemicals. In this study, fifteen (15) microalgal strains were screened and evaluated for their growth performance and the accumulation of macromolecules like polysaccharides and lipids under CO₂-enriched conditions, simulating the off-gas composition of an operational 2G biorefinery producing bioethanol from wastes. It was found that *Stichococcus* sp. exhibited the highest polysaccharides accumulation (33% *w/w*) in biomass, while *Chlorella vulgaris* demonstrated superior lipids content (34% *w/w*). Both strains (coded as wild-AUTH) displayed robust growth, each achieving biomass concentrations of 1.5 g/L of Dry Cell Weight (DCW), while maintaining tolerance to the gas feedstock. The protein contents of the strains further support their potential integration into a 3G biorefinery framework, where advanced biofuels could be one of multiple valorization pathways. These findings underline the feasibility of using microalgae as a retrofitting solution for bioethanol and other bioenergy plants, enhancing CO₂ capture while enabling biofuel production. The top-performing species provide a basis for optimizing bioprocess parameters and scaling up the cultivation in industrial photobioreactors (PBRs) to improve productivity and commercial applicability.

Keywords: microalgae; biofuels; *Stichococcus*; *Chlorella*; polysaccharides; lipids; biomass

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1. Introduction

Globally, climate change and increasing levels of CO₂ in the atmosphere are closely linked to the rise in anthropogenic activities, particularly the combustion of fossil fuels [1]. One of the key sectors contributing to this problem is transportation, with road, aviation, and maritime subsectors being all significant contributors [2]. According to the European Environment Agency (EEA), despite all the current measures in place, emissions—particularly from international traffic, including aviation and maritime transport—are expected to continue rising [3].

A sustainable and cost-effective approach to reduce CO₂ emissions is to capture and reuse this greenhouse gas (GHG) for microalgae cultivation, producing biomass that can then be transformed into advanced biofuels [4]. This approach fully aligns with initiatives like the European Green Deal and, specifically, with the package ‘Fit for 55’—The EU’s plan for a green transition [5]. Given these developments, microalgae today present a promising solution for the production of sustainable biofuels across various transportation sectors,

while simultaneously fixing substantial amounts of CO₂ through photosynthesis [6]; they are up to 50 times more effective than terrestrial plants, especially when cultivated in high-end photobioreactors [7]. Furthermore, microalgal biomass is a key renewable resource for producing sustainable aviation fuels (SAF), as well as biofuels for maritime transport, heavy-duty vehicles, and other transportation modes, through the transformation of lipids and other intracellularly produced biochemical compounds (macromolecules) within the framework of 3rd generation (3G) biorefineries [8]. Studies have shown that enriching microalgal cultures with gas mixtures or effluents containing high CO₂ levels can, to a certain extent, enhance their growth rate and biomass yield [9].

While in recent decades CO₂ bioconversion via microalgae has gained significant attention for the production of biofuels and mainly nutritional products, challenges remain, such as impurities in CO₂-laden streams that can hamper their growth, as well as the high energy demands of cultivation systems and downstream processing [10,11]. Additionally, microalgae often require stress conditions, such as nutrient(s) limitation, to accumulate valuable biochemicals like polysaccharides and/or lipids, which at the same time reduces the overall biomass productivity [12]. Combined with technological and economic barriers, including high production costs related to both Capital (CAPEX) and Operational (OPEX) Expenditures, as well as significant land use requirements for open (mainly) and closed systems, these hurdles have hindered the sustainable, large-scale deployment and widespread commercialization of this technology [13,14]. Despite these challenges, bioconversion of CO₂ through microalgae for reducing emissions and producing advanced biofuels remains a promising approach. Integrating individual production stages along the entire value chain—linking CO₂-emitting industries with the microalgae bioconversion process, while focusing on efficiently reducing energy, water, and land use requirements—is expected to create economically viable processes [15]. This integration is one of the primary goals for the future of the microalgae-based industry.

Within the vast diversity of microalgal species, which includes both eukaryotic genera such as *Chlorella* and *Stichococcus*, and prokaryotic genera like *Arthrospira*, significant potential for CO₂ capture and biomass production has been demonstrated. *Chlorella vulgaris*, for instance, has been extensively studied for its capacity to assimilate CO₂ and synthesize biomass rich in lipids, serving as precursors for biodiesel and other advanced biofuels [16]. In general, *Chlorella* sp. are historically among the most studied microalgae and are known for their robustness. They can be manipulated by adjusting nutritional conditions to accumulate either proteins or lipids; typically, nitrogen limitation is applied to induce lipids accumulation [17]. Following this principle, CO₂-rich gas streams are expected to enhance lipids production in *Chlorella* cultures. Similarly, species from the genus *Stichococcus* have been investigated for their CO₂ fixation capabilities. They are well-known for their ability to produce polysaccharides through a growth-associated mechanism [18], and have demonstrated resilience in cultures under non-ideal conditions, such as high CO₂ content in the gaseous feed stream [19]. This feature makes them suitable candidates for the bioremediation of industrial biogenic or fossil-based emissions. *Arthrospira* species, commonly known as Spirulina, have also been explored for CO₂ capture. These cyanobacteria are recognized for their high growth rates and ability to produce substantial biomass under CO₂-enriched conditions, serving here as model strains to study their behavior under varying CO₂ concentrations [20]. The produced biomass also contains valuable co-products such as proteins and pigments, adding economic value to the bioprocess due to their nutraceutical and cosmetic applications, among others [21]. Similarly, species from the order *Chlamydomonadales* are efficient at photosynthesis in diverse environments [22], while other *Chlorophyta* sp. are highly resilient and capable of accumulating substantial amounts of lipids, making them excellent candidates for biofuel production. *Komarekiella* species are

known for the simultaneous production of primary and secondary metabolites, making them ideal for biorefining applications [23]. In addition, microalgal species like *Scenedesmus*, and *Nannochloropsis*, among many others, have been studied for their dual role in CO₂ sequestration and biofuel production. Their tolerance to varying environmental conditions makes them suitable for integration with industrial processes where CO₂ emissions are prevalent [24–27].

The present work aims to build upon this existing knowledge by evaluating a selection of microalgal species for their efficiency in accumulating polysaccharides and/or lipids under conditions that mimic industrial CO₂ emissions. Along with these two macromolecules, accumulated proteins are also quantified to provide a comprehensive characterization of the strains. To this end, focus is placed not only on assessing the biofuel potential of these microalgae but also on evaluating their performance in environments reflective of real-world industrial settings. By doing so, we seek to identify strains that are not only effective in CO₂ capture and biofuel production but also resilient to the challenges posed by industrial effluents. Thus, screening experiments are conducted under industrially relevant conditions considering the source and composition of the CO₂-containing stream. The study focuses on the specific adaptation of microalgae to industrial CO₂-enriched off-gases, particularly from a 2nd generation (2G) bioethanol plant, and offers a detailed assessment of strain performance under real-world conditions, which is critical for the development of large-scale, sustainable biofuel production systems.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Microalgal Species

A comprehensive list of fifteen (15) microalgal strains (see Table 1) was prepared for screening and evaluation, based on their performance in the presence of industrial off-gases, specifically those from an operating 2G bioethanol plant. The selection criteria for these strains included viability, robustness, and tolerance to the GHG-laden gaseous feedstock, growth rate (expressed in biomass production and its maximum concentration), and the ability to accumulate polysaccharides and/or lipids.

Table 1. Shortlist of microalgal species screened and evaluated as potential polysaccharides and/or lipids producers in industrially relevant conditions.

Number (#), Microalgal Species, and Reference Code		
#1 <i>Stichococcus</i> sp. wild-TUC	#6 <i>Chlorella</i> sp. ACA17	#11 <i>Arthrospira fusiformis</i> TAU-MAC 0113
#2 <i>Stichococcus</i> sp. TAU-MAC 0119	#7 <i>Chlorella</i> sp. ASP14	#12 <i>Arthrospira maxima</i> TAU-MAC 0213
#3 <i>Stichococcus</i> sp. EMS1-TUC	#8 <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> TAU-MAC 1110	#13 <i>Chlamydomonadales</i> sp. TAU-MAC 3510
#4 <i>Stichococcus</i> sp. EMS3-TUC	#9 <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> TAU-MAC 3210	#14 <i>Chlorophyta</i> sp. TAU-MAC 3917
#5 <i>Stichococcus</i> sp. wild-AUTH	#10 <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> wild-AUTH	#15 <i>Komarekiella</i> sp. TAU-MAC 0117

All microalgal strains selected for screening were graciously provided by collaborating scholars from the Schools of Chemical Engineering and Biology at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, as well as the School of Chemical and Environmental Engineering at the Technical University of Crete, and the Department of Biology at the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece. Upon receipt, the strains were immediately re-cultivated in 100 mL flasks to prepare precultures for further experimentation and analysis.

Previous tests had been performed with all species to qualify them for inclusion in the shortlist of this study.

2.2. Microalgae Cultivation

All strains were cultivated in 500 mL conical (Erlenmeyer) flasks, placed in an orbital shaking incubator (GFL 3031, Burgwedel, Germany) at a controlled temperature below 25 °C, regulated by a cooling system (chiller) that circulated air inside the incubator. A gentle stirring frequency of 80 rpm was applied to ensure adequate mixing. Each flask was initially loaded with 185 mL of Bold Basal Modified (3N-BBM+V) cultivation medium, followed by inoculation with 15 mL from a mature preculture of each strain, resulting in an initial biomass concentration of approximately 0.1 g/L per flask. Note that 3N-BBM+V is a widely used chemically defined nutrient solution, designed to support the growth of various microalgal species by providing essential macro- and micro-nutrients in optimal and excess concentrations, promoting both cellular proliferation and metabolic activity. By using this medium, the effects of CO₂-laden conditions can be clearly assessed, as other nutritional factors that could potentially limit the growth of the selected strains are effectively ruled out. However, the cultivation conditions in the shaken flasks may not have excluded all potential growth-limiting factors due to the small volume and scale. The detailed chemical composition of 3N-BBM+V can be found in Table 2.

Table 2. Detailed composition of the chemically defined nutrient medium 3N-BBM+V used for cultivating the selected microalgal strains.

Major Components	Concentration (g/L)	Traces and Vitamins	Concentration (g/L)
NaNO ₃	0.75	DiNa-EDTA	0.0045
K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	0.075	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	0.000582
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.175	MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.000246
NaCl	0.025	ZnCl ₂	0.00003
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.075	CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.000012
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.025	Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.000024
		Vitamin B1	0.00012
		Vitamin B12	0.0001

Artificial illumination was provided to the flasks by eight (8) LED T8 lamps (11 W, 950 lumens, with an illumination intensity of 100 µmol/(m²·s)), mounted in a custom-designed lighting box, with a 16:8 h light/dark cycle to mimic natural photoperiods. To evaluate the tolerance of each strain to elevated CO₂ concentrations and other inhibitory compounds, a gaseous stream simulating the bioethanol production off-gases was continuously supplied to each culture at a flow rate of 80 mL/min. The composition of the gaseous stream (contained in a 50-bar pressurized cylinder procured from BUSE Gas S.A., Thessaloniki, Greece) was (*v/v*): 9.5% CO₂, 0.24% O₂, 100 ppm SO_x (as SO₂) and 20 ppm NO_x (as NO₂), balanced with N₂. This mixture reflects the composition of off-gases generated during bioethanol production at the Perseo Biotechnology S.L biorefinery (Valencia, Spain), diluted tenfold to reduce the concentration of CO₂ below the 10% *v/v* tolerance threshold [28]. Before entering the system, the gas mixture was sterilized via a 0.2 µm filter (Whatman plc, Maidstone, UK). The incubation period lasted 15 days, during which the growth rate of each culture was monitored by measuring its optical density (OD), as described in the subsequent section.

2.3. Monitoring and Analytical Measurements

Microalgae growth in all flask experiments was monitored by periodically collecting 2 mL from each culture for OD measurements at 600 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (U-1800, Hitachi, Tokyo, Japan). The chosen wavelength of 600 nm ensures minimal absorption from the nutrient medium, allowing for a more accurate representation of the microalgal biomass. If necessary, samples were diluted in cuvettes to ensure that the absorbance values fell within the linear response range and precision of the instrument (i.e., <1). Despite OD measurement being a quick and efficient method for estimating biomass growth and potentially concentration, it is important to note that OD readings may be influenced by changes in cell size and morphology throughout the growth phases, especially in high cell concentrations, or by the level of produced chlorophyll. This limits the direct correlation between OD and cell concentration or Dry Cell Weight (DCW). In this work, the OD values remained at relatively low-to-moderate values ensuring that it served as a reliable indicator of culture progression; a significant drop in OD often signaled cell inhibition or even death.

Biomass concentration of microalgal cultures was quantified as DCW using a gravimetric method. Specifically, culture samples (2–10 mL, depending on the density) were filtered through pre-weighed glass microfiber filters (934-AH, 1.5 µm pore diameter; Whatman plc, Maidstone, UK) to capture the cellular biomass. The filters were first washed with deionized water to remove excess salts from the nutrient medium and then dried overnight in an oven at a controlled temperature of 45 °C to ensure complete moisture removal. After drying, the filters were re-weighed, and the dry biomass was determined by calculating the difference.

Lipids quantification in microalgal biomass followed the Folch method [29]. 1 mL of a 2:1 *v/v* chloroform/methanol solution was added to approximately 6–7 mg of freeze-dried biomass. The suspension was placed in an ice bath and sonicated (Vibra Cell VC-505 Sonicator, Sonics & Materials, Inc., Newtown, CT, USA) for 10 min using a 1/8-inch diameter tip, set to 40% amplitude (45 s pulses followed by 15 s pauses to prevent overheating). After sonication, the suspension was centrifuged (10 min, 8000 × *g*) and the lipids-containing supernatant was transferred to a separate container. The remaining sediment underwent 2–3 re-extractions to maximize lipids recovery. Next, 1 mL of a 0.88% *w/v* KCl solution was added to the pooled supernatants, followed by centrifugation to remove residual solids. A small volume (0.3–0.9 mL) of an upper-phase solvent (chloroform/methanol/water in an 8:4:3 ratio), was added to the lipids-rich supernatant, followed by centrifugation and solvent removal. If needed, pure methanol was added to adjust the final volume to 4.5 mL. The lipids extract was placed on a pre-weighed glass plate and dried overnight at 45 °C. The plate was then re-weighed, and the lipids content was determined gravimetrically.

To determine the intracellular polysaccharides content, 1 mL of a 2.5 mol/L HCl solution was added to 2–3 mg of freeze-dried biomass sample, which was then incubated at 100 °C for 3 h. This acid hydrolysis process effectively ruptures microalgae cell walls, releasing the polysaccharides contained within. After incubation, the solution was allowed to cool before neutralizing with an equal volume of 2.5 mol/L. Following neutralization, the well-established phenol-sulfuric acid method [30] was employed to quantify the monomeric saccharides (sugars) content, expressed as glucose equivalents. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 483 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. D-glucose solutions of known concentrations served as reference standards.

For protein quantification, a freeze-dried biomass sample (2–3 mg) was initially dispersed in 10 mL of a 0.05 M phosphate buffer (PB) (pH = 7.4) and 0.5 N NaOH mixture containing 5% *v/v* methanol (MeOH) (R1). Ultrasonication using again the same apparatus (1/2 inch tip, 50% amplitude, 40 s pulses with 20 s pauses to avoid excess heat buildup)

was then applied in an ice-water bath to disrupt cell walls [31]. After sonication, 5 mL of R1 was added, bringing the total volume to 15 mL. The suspension was then heated at 100 °C for 30 min with constant stirring (280 rpm) to ensure complete protein extraction. The lysate was centrifuged ($20,000\times g$, 10 min), and the protein-containing supernatant was analyzed via the micro-BCA (bicinchoninic acid) method, by reducing Cu^{2+} to Cu^{+} and forming a purple complex with BCA, which is measured at 562 nm using the UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Protein concentration was determined using bovine serum albumin (BSA) standards (0.5–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) in 1% MeOH, 0.1 N NaOH.

The combined analysis of lipids, polysaccharides, and proteins enabled finally the calculation of total biochemical products (also mentioned in this study as total macromolecules = lipids + polysaccharides + proteins) and residual biomass in the microalgal cultures. To ensure accuracy and reproducibility, each strain was cultivated in duplicate flasks, with measurements performed on two technical replicates per biological replicate, resulting in a total of $n = 4$ replicates per condition (unless otherwise specified). Results are presented as mean values \pm standard errors (including error bars), calculated from these four independent samples for each measured variable.

3. Results

3.1. Microalgae Growth

To perform an initial evaluation of the fifteen (15) microalgal species, cell growth was monitored by periodically measuring the optical density (OD). These OD measurements allowed for indirect estimation of microalgae growth and biomass production throughout the cultivation period and also served as an indication of the cells' survivability. For the majority of the species, OD was successfully tracked and evaluated. However, for both *Arthrospira* species, accurate measurements could not be obtained due to non-homogeneous growth observed under high CO_2 concentration (9.5% v/v CO_2). Specifically, the cells of these two strains significantly aggregated, which is an unusual behavior for *Spirulina*. This uneven distribution of cells in the culture likely impacted the accuracy of OD measurements, rendering them unreliable for this particular strain. The OD curves of the remaining species, colored by strain(s) groups, are presented in Figure 1. This figure provides a comparative overview of the growth dynamics under the given experimental conditions, highlighting the variability in CO_2 tolerance and biomass productivity across the different microalgal species.

Among the microalgal strains evaluated, *Stichococcus* sp. wild-AUTH exhibited the highest final OD, reaching a peak value of approximately 14 after 15 days of cultivation, demonstrating robust growth under the experimental conditions. Following closely were three *Chlorella vulgaris* strains, i.e., *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH, *Chlorella vulgaris* TAU-MAC 1110, and *Chlorella vulgaris* TAU-MAC 3210, with OD values ranging between 10 and 12, indicating strong growth performance. Lower OD values were observed for the remaining *Stichococcus* sp. strains. Wild-TUC and TAU-MAC 0119 both exhibited steady growth and reached approximately an OD of 7. The final two *Stichococcus* sp. strains, namely EMS1-TUC and EMS3-TUC, displayed delayed and slower growth patterns. It is important to note that the latter two strains had been subjected to random evolution before being supplied/delivered for cultivation. This process may have negatively affected their tolerance and adaptability to stressful cultivation conditions, such as the ones applied here.

Figure 1. Optical Density (OD) results for the 15 microalgal species under study, cultivated in Erlenmeyer flasks with 9.5% *v/v* CO₂. Species numbers and names (corresponding also to Table 1): #1 *Stichococcus* sp. wild-TUC; #2 *Stichococcus* sp. TAU-MAC 0119; #3 *Stichococcus* sp. EMS1-TUC; #4 *Stichococcus* sp. EMS3-TUC; #5 *Stichococcus* sp. wild-AUTH; #6 *Chlorella* sp. ACA17; #7 *Chlorella* sp. ASP14; #8 *Chlorella vulgaris* TAU-MAC 1110; #9 *Chlorella vulgaris* TAU-MAC 3210; #10 *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH; #11 *Arthrospira fusiformis* TAU-MAC 0113; #12 *Arthrospira maxima* TAU-MAC 0213; #13 *Chlamydomonadales* sp. TAU-MAC 3510; #14 *Chlorophyta* sp. TAU-MAC 3917; and #15 *Komarekiella* sp. TAU-MAC 0117.

The two other *Chlorella* strains examined, *Chlorella* sp. ASP17 and *Chlorella* sp. ASP14, reached moderate values of OD, around 7. These strains appeared to enter the stationary phase after just one week of cultivation, suggesting slower adaptation to the high CO₂ content of the feedstock or early stagnation in their growth. This early transition to the stationary phase may have limited their overall biomass accumulation compared to the more robust strains. For the remaining species, generally low OD values were recorded, with most strains remaining below 2. Notably, *Chlamydomonadales* sp. TAU-MAC 3510 exhibited more robust growth compared to *Chlorophyta* sp. TAU-MAC 3917 and *Komarekiella* sp. TAU-MAC 0117, yet it still only reached a maximum OD value of approximately 1.6. The high CO₂ concentration clearly inhibited the growth of these strains, indicating unsuitability to thrive in CO₂-enriched environments like the industrial effluents studied in this work.

3.2. Biomass Production

A more accurate indication of microalgae viability and physiological state than OD measurements is biomass growth, which is quantified as DCW. Figure 2a illustrates the maximum DCW per strain, recorded at the point of peak growth for each of the investigated microalgal strains, as shown in the growth curves of Figure 1. The color groups in the figure provide a clearer comparison of the strain performance with similar characteristics,

making it easier to assess the influence of species-specific traits on biomass production under the given cultivation conditions.

Figure 2. Screening results for all investigated microalgal strains, cultivated in Erlenmeyer flasks with 9.5% *v/v* CO₂: (a) Biomass concentration (as Dry Cell Weight, DCW) on the day of highest OD value; (b) Polysaccharides content (% *w/w*) in DCW; (c) Lipids content (% *w/w*) in DCW; and (d) Proteins content (% *w/w*) in DCW.

Several of the investigated strains, including some *Stichococcus* sp., all *Chlorella* sp. and *Chlorella vulgaris* strains, as well as *Arthrospira* and *Chlamydomonadales* sp. TAU-MAC 3510, exhibited no significant growth inhibition in response to elevated CO₂ levels. Notably, two *Stichococcus* strains, wild-TUC and TAU-MAC 0119, demonstrated the ability to accumulate more than 1 g/L of biomass, with *Stichococcus* sp. wild-AUTH achieving the highest biomass concentration of approximately 1.5 g/L (average productivity of 0.1 g/(L·day)).

These findings are consistent with the discussion on OD measurements. On the other hand, the growth of *Stichococcus* sp. EMS1-TUC and EMS3-TUC appeared to be inhibited by the excess CO₂ during cultivation, leading to lower biomass accumulation. Moreover, all *Chlorella* strains demonstrated robust growth, with biomass concentrations exceeding 1 g/L. *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH achieved the highest biomass concentration in this group with approximately 1.5 g/L (average productivity of 0.1 g/(L·day)). As with the discussion on OD results, this again provides a second clear indication that this particular species may be sufficiently tolerant and robust for potential application in industrially relevant conditions.

As for the remaining microalgal species, *Arthrospira* cf. *fusiformis* TAU-MAC 0113 produced a notable biomass concentration of approximately 0.9 g/L (average productivity of 0.06 g/(L·day)), while *Arthrospira maxima* TAU-MAC 0213 reached slightly lower levels of around 0.75 g/L (average productivity of 0.05 g/(L·day)). However, a challenge with these strains was the formation of non-homogeneous cultures during cultivation, which may have impacted the consistency of their growth and measurement accuracy. This may affect both OD and DCW measurements, possibly due to inadequate or non-representative sampling of the entire culture, leading to inconsistencies and inaccurate correlations between these values. Of the remaining strains, *Chlamydomonadales* sp. TAU-MAC 3510 was the only one to achieve a biomass concentration close to 1 g/L. In contrast, *Chlorophyta* sp. TAU-MAC 3917 and *Komarekiella* sp. TAU-MAC 0117 exhibited poor growth, with final biomass concentrations below 0.5 g/L (average productivity of 0.033 g/(L·day)).

It should be noted that in all cultures, the medium pH was not controlled but was measured dynamically and remained constant at 6.5 ± 0.2 . This stable pH is primarily due to the excess supply of CO₂, which minimized the effect on the equilibrium between the gas and liquid phases, as well as the phosphate buffer present in the cultivation medium. The buffer system ensured that any pH variation due to CO₂ addition was minimal. Consequently, pH had little impact on microbial growth, as it remained within the suitable range for all the microalgal strains tested. Additionally, while nitrate utilization can also cause pH shifts, the buffering capacity of the medium ensured that microbial growth was not hindered by any potential alkalinity changes resulting from nitrogen assimilation.

3.3. Biochemical Products Accumulation

Following the preliminary screening of the species for their growth and biomass production performance under elevated CO₂ conditions, a similar comparison was conducted to assess their ability to accumulate polysaccharides, lipids, and proteins. While polysaccharides and lipids are more relevant to biofuel production, protein accumulation was also analyzed as a complementary aspect of this study. Initially, Figure 2b presents the content (% w/w) of polysaccharides in the biomass of the investigated microalgal strains cultivated under excess CO₂ conditions. All *Stichococcus* strains demonstrated a strong ability to accumulate polysaccharides, with a relevant content ranging between approximately 30% and 40% w/w of biomass concentration. Notably, *Stichococcus* sp. TAU-MAC 0119 and *Stichococcus* sp. EMS3-TUC exhibited the highest polysaccharide accumulation, reaching 35.78% w/w and 39.02% w/w, respectively. In contrast, the majority of the other microalgal strains (including all *Chlorella* strains, *Arthrospira maxima*, *Chlorophyta* sp., and *Komarekiella* sp.) showed more moderate polysaccharides accumulation, with values ranging between 20% and 25%, while *Arthrospira* cf. *fusiformis* TAU-MAC 0113 and *Chlorophyta* sp. TAU-MAC 3917 only accumulated around 15% w/w.

In terms of lipids accumulation, all studied *Chlorella* strains demonstrated a strong ability to accumulate lipids in their biomass (ranging from 30% to 35% w/w), except for *Chlorella vulgaris* TAU-MAC 3210, which contained approximately 26% w/w (Figure 2c).

Additionally, several other microalgal strains exhibited comparable or even higher lipids accumulation, e.g., *Stichococcus* sp. EMS3-TUC with around 32% *w/w* lipids, and *Chlorophyta* sp. TAU-MAC 3917 and *Komarekiella* sp. TAU-MAC 0117 with approximately 41% and 32% *w/w* content, respectively. Among the *Stichococcus* strains, most showed a relatively low lipids content of around 25% *w/w*, except for EMS3-TUC, which interestingly stood out.

With regard to protein content, several of the studied microalgal strains exhibited notable accumulation patterns. As expected, *Arthrospira* cf. *fusiformis* TAU-MAC 0113, *Arthrospira maxima* TAU-MAC 0213, but also *Chlamydomonadales* sp. TAU-MAC 3510 were the top performers, with protein levels reaching approximately 49%, 40%, and 36% *w/w*, respectively (Figure 2d). Even under these less favorable conditions, clearly *Spirulina* is an adequate producer of valuable proteins. Among the *Stichococcus* strains, protein content ranged between 22–27% *w/w*, with the exception of EMS3-TUC, which produced approximately 33% *w/w* in the cells. As for the *Chlorella* strains, they consistently reached protein accumulation in the range of 27% to 30% *w/w*. *Chlorophyta* sp. TAU-MAC 3917 and *Komarekiella* sp. TAU-MAC 0117 also demonstrated moderate protein accumulation, each reaching around 27% *w/w*.

With the above findings, the total percentage of major biochemical/macromolecular products (polysaccharides, lipids and proteins) accumulated by the microalgae can be calculated, along with the residual biomass content (which includes ash, chlorophylls and other pigments, other bioactive compounds, absorbed water, etc.). This allows evaluation of both biomass composition and total titers of each compound in the culture, which is crucial for several reasons. While compositions provide insights into the relative distribution of biochemical compounds within the microalgal biomass, concentration data offer a more practical perspective for large-scale applications. Concentrations directly indicate the absolute amount of each biochemical product that can be harvested per unit of culture volume, which is a key factor in determining the overall productivity and economic viability of any microalgal cultivation system. Table 3 presents respectively the concentrations of the targeted measured biochemical products.

Upon examining the concentrations of polysaccharides accumulated by the investigated microalgae strains, three cultures demonstrated significant polysaccharides production, reaching concentrations of approximately 0.4–0.5 g/L, namely *Stichococcus* sp. wild-AUTH (0.5 g/L), *Stichococcus* sp. wild-TUC culture (0.45 g/L), and *Stichococcus* sp. TAU-MAC 0119 (0.4 g/L). In contrast, the remaining two *Stichococcus* strains produced significantly lower amounts of polysaccharides per culture, accumulating less than half the values achieved by the top three strains.

On the other hand, all of the studied *Chlorella* cultures demonstrated consistent polysaccharide production, with concentrations around 0.3 g/L. Specifically, *Chlorella* sp. ASP14 culture reached approximately 0.32 g/L of polysaccharides, followed by *Chlorella vulgaris* TAU-MAC 3210 and *Chlorella* sp. ACA17 cultures, which accumulated 0.3 g/L and 0.29 g/L, respectively. The other two *Chlorella* cultures, wild-AUTH and *C. vulgaris* TAU-MAC 1110 achieved slightly lower concentrations, with values of approximately 0.28 g/L and 0.26 g/L, respectively. However, none of these could match the three top-performing *Stichococcus* sp. Of the remaining microalgal strains only *Komarekiella* sp. TAU-MAC 0117 was able to accumulate polysaccharides at a concentration exceeding 0.2 g/L. The other four cultures did not surpass this concentration, indicating more limited polysaccharides production potential, coupled with poor biomass growth performance.

Among the strains studied for lipids production, *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH culture is the only one producing approximately 0.5 g/L of lipids. The other *Chlorella* cultures demonstrated lower lipids accumulation, achieving concentrations only up to 0.4 g/L. Specifically, *C. ASP14*, *ACA17*, and *vulgaris* TAU-MAC 1110 produced 0.43, 0.41, and

0.38 g/L of lipids, respectively. Finally, *C. vulgaris* TAU-MAC 3210 culture reached a lower lipids concentration of only 0.28 g/L. All remaining microalgal cultures accumulated low levels of lipids, with concentrations below 0.3 g/L.

Table 3. Concentrations per culture of all individual and total biochemical products (total macromolecules: polysaccharides, lipids, and proteins) produced by the 15 studied strains.

Microalgal Species	Polysaccharides (g/L)	Lipids (g/L)	Proteins (g/L)	Total Macromolecules (g/L)
<i>Stichococcus</i> sp. wild-TUC	0.44 ± 0.013	0.35 ± 0.039	0.34 ± 0.043	1.13 ± 0.095
<i>Stichococcus</i> sp. TAU-MAC 0119	0.39 ± 0.016	0.30 ± 0.025	0.29 ± 0.036	0.98 ± 0.077
<i>Stichococcus</i> sp. EMS1-TUC	0.13 ± 0.020	0.11 ± 0.009	0.14 ± 0.016	0.38 ± 0.045
<i>Stichococcus</i> sp. EMS3-TUC	0.16 ± 0.032	0.13 ± 0.011	0.09 ± 0.009	0.38 ± 0.052
<i>Stichococcus</i> sp. wild-AUTH	0.48 ± 0.036	0.36 ± 0.040	0.36 ± 0.045	1.2 ± 0.121
<i>Chlorella</i> sp. ACA17	0.29 ± 0.033	0.41 ± 0.034	0.40 ± 0.044	1.1 ± 0.111
<i>Chlorella</i> sp. ASP14	0.32 ± 0.038	0.43 ± 0.039	0.37 ± 0.046	1.12 ± 0.123
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> TAU-MAC 1110	0.26 ± 0.028	0.38 ± 0.032	0.33 ± 0.037	0.97 ± 0.097
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> TAU-MAC 3210	0.30 ± 0.010	0.28 ± 0.026	0.28 ± 0.035	0.86 ± 0.071
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> wild-AUTH	0.28 ± 0.011	0.49 ± 0.061	0.42 ± 0.047	1.19 ± 0.119
<i>Arthrospira fusiformis</i> TAU-MAC 0113	0.08 ± 0.037	0.21 ± 0.021	0.44 ± 0.040	0.73 ± 0.098
<i>Arthrospira maxima</i> TAU-MAC 0213	0.10 ± 0.049	0.17 ± 0.022	0.30 ± 0.033	0.57 ± 0.104
<i>Chlamydomonadales</i> sp. TAU-MAC 3510	0.12 ± 0.016	0.19 ± 0.019	0.34 ± 0.034	0.65 ± 0.069
<i>Chlorophyta</i> sp. TAU-MAC 3917	0.18 ± 0.020	0.21 ± 0.023	0.14 ± 0.016	0.53 ± 0.059
<i>Komarekiella</i> sp. TAU-MAC 0117	0.24 ± 0.053	0.13 ± 0.014	0.11 ± 0.009	0.48 ± 0.076

In the interest of providing a comprehensive characterization of the studied microalgal strains, protein concentration in the culture of each species was also calculated. The results revealed three strains that were able to accumulate over 0.4 g/L of proteins: *A. cf. fusiformis* TAU-MAC, *C. vulgaris* wild-AUTH, and *C. ACA17*. Several other cultures reached protein concentrations ranging from 0.3 to 0.37 g/L, including *S. wild-AUTH* and wild-TUC, *C. ASP14* and *C. vulgaris* TAU-MAC 1110, and *C. sp.* TAU-MAC 3510. The cultures of the remaining strains had protein concentrations below 0.3 g/L.

4. Discussion

Each microalgal species and variant investigated in this study demonstrated unique growth characteristics when exposed to CHG-laden conditions, which can be leveraged to meet biofuel production objectives. This resilience is a hallmark of microalgae, which can acclimate to diverse environments and efficiently capture and convert CO₂ into valuable biomass [32]. The strains were selected based on key criteria such as final biomass concen-

tration, maximum polysaccharides and lipids contents, and the general ability to thrive in CO₂-enriched environments, reflecting industrial off-gases.

The comparative results are shown in the bubble graphs of Figure 3, which display species capable of efficiently accumulating polysaccharides (Figure 3a) and lipids (Figure 3b), alongside adequate biomass production in the top-right quadrant. Among the strains tested, *Stichococcus* sp. wild-AUTH emerged as the top performer for biomass production, reaching a concentration of approximately 1.5 g/L DCW. This strain also accumulated significant amounts of polysaccharides (around 33% *w/w*), which is essential for biofuel production, as polysaccharides can be converted into fermentable sugars for bioethanol production [33]. Additionally, *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH exhibited the highest lipids concentration (approximately 34% *w/w*), making it an ideal candidate for biofuels derived from lipids, such as biodiesel and advanced biofuels based on hydrocarbons [34].

A key finding from this study is that several microalgal strains, including *Stichococcus* sp., *Chlorella* sp., and *Arthrospira* sp., showed minimal growth inhibition in response to elevated CO₂ concentrations and other greenhouse gases, supporting their potential for cultivation in industrial environments. These results align with previous studies demonstrating the adaptability of certain microalgal strains to high CO₂ concentrations [35–37]. Notably, *Stichococcus* sp. wild-AUTH stood out as the best candidate for polysaccharides production, while *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH excelled in lipids accumulation. While *Arthrospira* and *Chlamydomonadales* sp. TAU-MAC 3510 also performed well under CO₂-enriched conditions in terms of biomass production [38], their lower polysaccharides and lipids contents suggest limited potential for biofuel applications. Instead, they may serve as valuable producers of proteins [39]. Interestingly, strains like *Chlorophyta* sp. and *Ko-marekiella* sp. exhibited lower biomass yields, yet their moderate protein accumulation (20–30% *w/w*) highlights their potential for other biotechnological applications [40].

The results of this study underscore also the importance of optimizing cultivation conditions for each microalgal strain to maximize both biomass yield and the accumulation of target biochemical products. They indicate that polysaccharides and lipids accumulation varied significantly between species, which can be attributed to the specific stress conditions applied during cultivation. Strains like *Stichococcus* sp. and *Chlorella vulgaris* performed exceptionally well in terms of polysaccharides and lipids accumulation, respectively. However, the need for further optimization of cultivation conditions, particularly nutrient stress and/or light exposure, remains evident [41]. The application of multiple stress factors—such as elevated CO₂ concentrations, light intensity, and N/P limitations—has been shown to be beneficial in enhancing lipids production in *Chlorella* sp. This result aligns with studies suggesting that high CO₂ concentrations can act as a form of stress, driving metabolic shifts that favor lipids accumulation [42].

However, it is crucial to note that optimizing conditions for one macromolecule (e.g., lipids) may inadvertently compromise the accumulation of another (e.g., polysaccharides), thereby affecting the overall efficiency of the bioprocess. This trade-off needs to be carefully considered when developing biorefinery strategies. An optimized cultivation strategy for lipids production could involve the simultaneous application of multiple stress factors, which may enhance lipids yield but require balancing with other biochemical product yields [43]. Moreover, polysaccharides are typically of lower priority for microalgae producers, often ranked third after proteins and lipids, or even fourth after pigments or other bioactive compounds. As a result, cultivation conditions are rarely optimized specifically for polysaccharide production [44]. Our study demonstrates that the accumulation of polysaccharides in *Stichococcus* sp. strains significantly contributes to the overall biomass composition, highlighting its potential for biofuel applications and other processes that utilize sugars. This characteristic is particularly valuable when considering the validated

growth-associated mechanism of polysaccharide production in this species, which enables maximum sugar production rates during bioprocess intensification.

Figure 3. Bubble graphs for: (a) Polysaccharides; and (b) Lipids; accumulation contents (% w/w) with respect to biomass concentration (as Dry Cell Weight, DCW—g/L), for all investigated microalgae strains, cultivated in Erlenmeyer flasks with excess CO₂ (9.5% v/v). Notice that in Figure 3b, the data points for *Stichococcus* sp. EMS1-TUC and *Komarekiella* sp. TAU-MAC 0117 coincide.

While numerous studies have already investigated the potential of microalgae to capture CO₂ from various gas streams, such as those from coal power plants or other industrial facilities [20,45], this work focused specifically on bioethanol plant off-gases, a significant source of industrial biogenic emissions. Previous studies have demonstrated the high CO₂ tolerance of certain microalgal strains like *Chlorella* and *Arthrospira* under flue gas conditions [46,47]. However, this research expanded on this by evaluating growth rates and also quantifying the accumulation of key biochemical products such as polysaccharides and lipids, which are critical precursors for biofuel production. Additionally, the complexities of optimizing cultivation for both lipids and polysaccharides are overcome [48], by specifically addressing the challenges of maximizing these macromolecules within two different industrially relevant strains under CO₂ excess. Thus, a deeper insight into the interactions between elevated CO₂ and other potential stressors (e.g., NO_x, SO_x) is provided, under industrial gas emissions.

Although the findings above highlight the strains' potential for industrial-scale cultivation under real-world conditions with multiple off-gases, a unified biorefinery approach that aims to optimize the simultaneous extraction of both polysaccharides and lipids simultaneously from a single strain, presents clear challenges. This is reflected in the biomass composition distribution for the two selected species, as can be determined from the results of Figure 2, which presents contrasting levels of polysaccharides and lipids in each strain (data in % w/w of DCW): polysaccharides 32.16%, lipids 24.84%, proteins 24.48% and residual biomass 18.52% for *Stichococcus* sp., and polysaccharides 19.18%, lipids 33.56%, proteins 28.77% and residual biomass 18.49% for *Chlorella vulgaris*. This reinforces the notion that specialized approaches are often necessary, where different strains are assigned to distinct value chains: polysaccharides-producing strains can be used for bioethanol production through sugars fermentation while lipids-producing strains can be processed for biodiesel and advanced biofuels production via esterification or hydroprocessing. While the flask-scale experiments conducted in this study provided valuable insights, it is expected that the yields of both polysaccharides and lipids will be further optimized in photobioreactor (PBR) systems. PBRs provide better-controlled conditions, which should enhance overall biomass yield and the accumulation of biochemical products [49]. Scaling up the cultivation process using PBRs should lead to improved efficiency and product concentration, further supporting the industrial feasibility of these strains.

In the context of a biorefinery, it may seem ideal to streamline the upstream cultivation process by focusing on a single species capable of producing both polysaccharides and lipids. However, as shown in this study, this approach presents significant challenges in both upstream and downstream processing. Achieving a global optimum for both macromolecules is often not feasible, and cascade extraction and purification steps for both products may compromise the integrity of either polysaccharides or lipids [50]. Moreover, in a biorefinery setting where multiple high-value biochemical products are targeted, the inherent trade-offs between lipids and polysaccharides production and recovery can affect overall efficiency and yield. Optimizing conditions for one product may inhibit the accumulation of the other, complicating the balance necessary for an efficient bioprocess.

Undoubtedly, the strains *Stichococcus* sp. and *Chlorella vulgaris* show the greatest potential for biofuel applications. Their ability to accumulate significant amounts of polysaccharides and lipids, respectively, under CO₂-enriched conditions makes them ideal candidates for industrial-scale applications. However, further optimization of cultivation conditions and scaling up to PBRs will be necessary to unlock their full potential for large-scale CO₂ capture and biofuel production.

5. Conclusions

Microalgae's ability to thrive in GHG-enriched environments, combined with their capacity to accumulate valuable biochemical products, positions them as a critical asset for sustainable biofuel production and CO₂ emission reduction. The primary objective of this study was to identify microalgal species suitable for producing polysaccharides and lipids when cultivated in off-gases from a 2G biorefinery dedicated to bioethanol production. Among the 15 strains tested, *Stichococcus* sp. wild-AUTH emerged as the best-performing strain for polysaccharide accumulation, reaching more than 30% in biomass, while *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH exhibited the highest lipids content (34%), making it an excellent candidate for biofuel applications. Notably, both strains demonstrated robust growth and resilience to the high CO₂ concentrations in the off-gas mixture, highlighting their suitability for industrial-scale cultivation in CO₂-rich environments.

The findings demonstrate that *Stichococcus* sp. and *Chlorella vulgaris* wild-AUTH are not only capable of accumulating the desired macromolecules but also show high tolerance to the complex off-gas mixture, making them ideal candidates for large-scale CO₂ capture and biofuels production. These strains have the potential to contribute to the development of efficient and sustainable biofuel production systems. Moreover, the comprehensive analysis of the strains' biochemical content provides valuable insights for future efforts to optimize microalgal cultivation conditions in photobioreactors and biorefinery systems.

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